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The Overburden of the Cost of Housing in the Italian Regions during the Period 2004-2021

It decreased by 41.81%

Istat calculates the overload of the cost of housing. The variable is defined as the percentage of people living in families where the total cost of the home in which they live represents more than 40% of the net family income. The data analyzed refers to the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the cost of housing in 2021. Campania is in first place by value of the cost of housing in 2021 with an amount equal to 11.6 units, followed by Sicily with a value of 9.5 units, from Puglia with an amount of 8.76 units. In the middle of the table we find Lazio with a value of 6.5 units, followed by Basilicata with an amount of 6.3 units and Veneto with a value of 5.7 units. Sardinia closes the ranking with an amount of 4.3 units, followed by Marche with a value of 3.6 units and Molise with an amount of 3.00 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the overload cost of housing between 2004 and 2021. Basilicata is in first place for percentage change in the cost of housing between 2004 and 2021 with a change equal to an amount of -17.11% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 7.6 units up to a value of 6.3 units. Sicily follows with a variation of -20.83% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 12 units to a value of 9.5 units. In third place is Puglia with a reduction in the value of the housing cost overload equal to an amount of -21.62% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.1 units in 2004 up to a value of 8.7 units in 2021. In the middle of the table are Liguria with a variation equal to an amount of -41.10% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 14.6 units up to a value of 8.6 units between 2004 and 2021 Valle d'Aosta follows with a variation equal to an amount of -43.30% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 9.7 units in 2004 up to a value of 5.5 units in 2021. Sardinia follows with a percentage change equal to an amount of -44.87% corresponding to a decrease from an amount of 7.8 units in 2004 to a value of 4.3 units in 2021. Lazio closes the ranking with a change equal to one amount of -57.79% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 15.4 units in 2004 up to a value of 6.5 units in 2021 or equal to a variation of 8.9 units. Marche follows with a variation equal to an amount of -59.55% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 8.9 units up to a value of 3.6 units between 2004 and 2021. Emilia closes the ranking Romagna with a variation equal to an amount of -63.56% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.8 units in 2004 up to a value of 4.3 units in 2021. Between 2004 and 2021 the average value of overloading the cost of housing decreased in the Italian regions by 41%, going from an amount of 10.94 units to a value of 6.36%.

The housing cost overload in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. The value of the housing cost overload decreased in all macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. It decreased in particular in the North -East of 54.31%, in Central Italy of 49.21%, in the North of 45.9%, in the

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North-West of 40.16%, in Southern Italy of 30.71%, in the South of 28.93 %, in the Islands 25.45%. The gaps between North and South in terms of housing cost overload are quite small, especially when compared with other socio-economic variables. The value of the housing cost overload in Southern Italy is equal to 1.3 times the corresponding value in the North, 1.13 times the value in the North-West, 1.62 times the value in the North-East, 1.34 times the value of Central Italy. Therefore it is possible to note a generalized reduction in the value of the housing cost overload in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021 with a marginal difference between Northern and Southern Italy.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data highlights the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Marche, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Trentino Alto Adige, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta, Veneto, Basilicata, Abruzzo, Tuscany, Puglia, Molise, Sardinia, Emilia-Romagna, Lombardy, Calabria, Piedmont;
- Cluster 2: Campania, Sicily, Liguria, Lazio.

From the clustering analysis we can note the dominance of cluster 2 compared to cluster 1 in terms of average value. The following cluster ordering therefore derives, i.e. $C2 > C1$. We can note that the clusters are very heterogeneous from an economic, social and institutional point of view. However, there is a tendency towards convergence of the Italian regions within cluster 1, i.e. the cluster with the lowest housing cost overhead, compared to cluster 2 where the value of the housing cost overhead is instead higher. It therefore follows that the value Campania, Sicily, Liguria and Lazio are regions in which there is a significant divergence between wages and the cost of housing. These are regions in which two phenomena could coexist: a low level of wages together with a concentration of real estate ownership oriented towards building speculation.

Conclusions. The value of the cost of housing overload decreased in all Italian regions and macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. Furthermore, the value of the cost of housing in the southern macro-regions is only marginally higher than the corresponding value of northern regions. The only regions that show a high level of housing costs are Campania, Sicily, Liguria and Lazio. The high values of the housing cost overload highlight on the one hand a reduced level of wages and on the other hand a tendency towards speculation in the cost of housing. It is probable that the regions in which there is a growth in the cost of housing are on the one hand behind in terms of the efficiency of the labor markets and on the other hand characterized by a high concentration of property ownership.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

■ Campania ■ Sicilia ■ Puglia ■ Liguria ■ Trentino-Alto Adige ■ Toscana ■ Lombardia ■ Piemonte ■ Lazio ■ Basilicata
■ Veneto ■ Valle d'Aosta ■ Calabria ■ Friuli-Venezia Giulia ■ Umbria ■ Abruzzo ■ Emilia-Romagna ■ Sardegna ■ Marche
■ Molise

